

INFLUENCE OF STORAGE PERIOD ON SENSORY QUALITIES AND MICROBIAL COUNT OF BEETROOT-PUMPKIN MIXED JAM

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(MS Received: 26.11.2023; MS Revised:30.12.2023; MS Accepted:02.01.2024)

MS 3148

(RESEARCH PAPER IN VEGETABLE SCIENCE)

Abstract

An experiment entitled, “influence of storage period on sensory qualities and microbial count of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam”, in the pursuit to find out best treatment on the basis of its sensory attributes, an extensive experiment was meticulously conducted during academic year 2022. This meticulous study took place at the Department of Vegetable Science, Dr. PDKV, Akola, employing a Completely Randomized Design to evaluate the effect different beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio with sugar and jaggery as sweetening agents on sensory qualities of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam during 120 days of storage. The primary objective of this experiment was to discern the most stable treatment on the basis of its sensory attributes, which obtain overall high sensory score. The treatments encompassed different beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio with different sweetening agents. The outcomes unveiled fascinating insights. Notably, treatment (T6) having 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent obtained maximum score in all sensory attributes and showed minimum microbial growth. Meanwhile, treatment (T4) having 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp and sugar as sweetening agent scored overall minimum score and showed maximum microbial growth.

Keywords: Beetroot-pumpkin, Mixed jam, Microbial count, Sensory qualities, Storage period.

Introduction

Beetroot is the taproot portion of a beet plant, usually known in North America as beets while the vegetable is referred to as beetroot in British English and also known as the table beet, garden beet, red beet, dinner beet or golden beet. Beetroot can be roasted, boiled or steamed, peeled, and then eaten warm with or without butter as a delicacy; cooked, pickled, and then eaten cold as a condiment; or peeled, shredded raw, and then eaten as a salad. Pickled beetroot is a traditional food in many country. In Indian cuisine, chopped, cooked, spiced beetroot is a common side dish. Yellow-coloured beetroots are grown on a very small scale for home consumption. . When beetroot juice is used, it is most stable in foods with a low water content, such as frozen novelties and fruit fillings. Juice prepared from beetroot served as dietary nitrate supplements (Berry *et al.*, 2015).

Pumpkin (*Cucurbita moschata*) is a gourd-like squash of the genus *Cucurbita* belongs to the family of *Cucurbitaceae*. *Cucurbita moschata* are the worldwide commonly grown species of pumpkin, it represents economically important species because of its high production. Pumpkins are extensively grown in tropical and subtropical countries. Pumpkin has received considerable attention in recent years for the sake of providing the human body his nutritional needs because of its healthy nutritional benefit where it is rich in vitamins, minerals and pectin, contains beneficial fatty acids and amino acids, it is considered to be a good source of carotenoids and a very rich source of carotene, mainly β -carotene which gives its yellow or orange colour. Consumption of foods containing carotene helps in prevention of eye disorders, cancer and skin diseases. It is considered to be a major source of vitamin A and so incorporation of β -carotene rich foods in diets is the best measure to improve vitamin A nutrition of individuals to overcome the problems and diseases caused by vitamin A deficiency (VAD). Also, pumpkin species reported to have pharmacological characteristics including anti-oxidant, lipid-lowering, protective, anti-microbial and anti-diabetic properties and anti-obesity properties (Kim *et al.*, 2012).

Mixed jams are popular among all, which are generally blend of different fruits or fruits and vegetable. Mixed vegetable jam is totally new concept with double nutritional benefits of vegetables.

Jam prepared with beetroot-pumpkin with different sweetening agents have high potential as nutritional as well as tasty food product. Most of the time we ignore nutritional potential of beetroot rather than utilized it salad or food colorant, in case of pumpkin it mostly used in curries and pancakes. Present product is prepared with mixture of both the healthy vegetables with different sweetening

agent which make it more palatable and boosts the utilization of beetroot and pumpkin in better way. Beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam have double benefits as it have goodness of both the vegetables, it provide healthy breakfast option, it is good for all ages, it can be utilized to tackle malnutrition as well as anemia in women. It is good for diabetic patients as prepared with jaggery as sweetening agent.

Material and Methods**Preparation of Beetroot-Pumpkin pulp**

Matured beetroot and pumpkin were selected for preparation of jam. On the day of preparation both, beetroot and pumpkin washed under portable running water and subsequently soaked for 10 minutes. Peeled of both beetroot and pumpkin, In pumpkin seed was separated, cleaned beetroot and pumpkin were cut down into small pieces separately boiled up to half hour in case of beetroot and 20 minutes for pumpkin on a low flame, followed by grinding. Extracted formulation of two pulps mixed in given proportion with the sugar and jaggery and heated with continuous stirring, while stirring citric acid was added and judged the end point by refractometer at 68 °B.

Preparation of Mixed jam

Different proportion of beetroot-pumpkin pulp mixed together as per treatments and boiled with sweetening agent and citric acid with continuous stirring upto end point that is 68 °B obtained on hand refractometer, sheet test or drop test.

The mixed jam was stored at ambient temperature and observations were recorded up to 120 days of storage at 30 days interval.

Sensory evaluation

The sensory properties of the beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam made from beetroot-pumpkin, including colour and appearance, texture, taste, flavour, and overall acceptability for fresh jam, were assessed at intervals of 30 days over the course of four months. The five semi trained panellists who made up the sensory evaluation panel were given samples of the jam and asked to rate them using the hedonic scale and reported mean values of the sensory evaluation score were calculated.

Microbial spoilage

Jam bottles were kept at room temperature after 120 days, the development of microbiological growth was checked and counted with the help of manual colony counter and documented down.

Results and Discussion**Colour and appearance**

Colour and appearance is an important sensory attribute to every food. Because it directly affects the overall acceptability of product. Table 1 showed the data which were recorded at 30, 60, 90 and 120

days after storage showed maximum score i.e. 8.7, 8.4, 8.2 and 8.1 respectively and overall maximum average score 8.4 after 120 days of storage was recorded in treatment T₆ with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent. This is confirmation with the findings of Rahman *et al.* (2013) in aloe vera, pineapple and mango blended jam.

Texture

Texture is another important sensory attribute to every food as it directly affects the overall acceptability of product. Data regarding texture of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam is presented in Table 2. At 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after storage showed maximum score i.e. 9.1, 9.0, 8.9 and 8.8 respectively and overall maximum average score 9.0 after 120 days of storage was recorded in treatment T₆ with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent. However minimum average score 7.8 recorded in treatment T₄ with 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and sugar as sweetening agent. It might be due to effect of sugars during the storage period and moisture percentage present in the jam. The results mentioned above are in conformity with the findings of Basu *et al.* (2007) in pineapple jam and Shahnawaz *et al.* (2011) in jamun jam.

Taste

Taste is a main sensory attribute of every food product. Data regarding taste of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam is presented in Table 3. At 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after storage showed maximum score were recorded i.e. 9.1, 8.8, 8.6 and 8.7 respectively and overall maximum average score 8.8 after 120 days of storage was recorded in treatment T₆ with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent. However overall minimum average score 7.4 was recorded in treatment T₄ with 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and sugar as sweetening agent. This is might be due to optimum content of sugar in jam as sugar is one of the most important ingredient in taste of jam. The result are in confirmation of the findings of Kopjar *et al.* (2009) in strawberry jam and Sucharitha *et al.* (2013) in ber-pineapple jam.

Flavour

Data regarding flavour of beetroot-pumpkin mixed is presented in Table 4. At 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after storage showed maximum score i.e.9.0, 8.9, 8.7 and 8.7 respectively and overall maximum average score 8.8 after 120 days of storage was recorded in treatment T₆ with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening

agent. However overall minimum average score 7.4 was recorded in treatment T₄ with 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and sugar as sweetening agent. Changes in flavour during storage period due to chemical reaction with organic acids present in pulp constituents. The results mentioned above are in conformity with the findings of Mahomud *et al.* (2008) in papaya jam and Chorage *et al.* (2020) in guava jam.

Overall acceptability

Data pertaining to overall acceptability of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam is presented in Table 5. At 30, 60, 90 and 120 days after storage showed maximum score were recorded i.e. 9.0, 8.8, 8.7, and 8.5 respectively and overall maximum average score 8.8 after 120 days of storage was recorded in treatment T₆ with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent. However overall minimum average score 7.4 was recorded in treatment T₄ with 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and sugar as sweetening agent. Overall acceptability score depends on appearance, colour, taste and texture score of the product. Since this parameters scored highest point for overall acceptability for jam. However during storage the score decreases. This is in confirmation with the findings of Rahman *et al.* (2013) in aloe vera, pineapple and mango blended jam and Banas *et al.* (2018) in gooseberry jam.

Microbial count

The results in Table 6 showed that maximum microbial growth found in treatments with sugar as sweetening agent as compared to treatments with jaggery as sweetening agent. Maximum yeasts and moulds growth was recorded 14.33×10^3 in treatment T₄ with 50:50 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio after 120 days of storage. However, minimum yeasts and moulds growth was recorded 9.3×10^3 in treatment T₆ having 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio.

This might be due to food products are microbiologically stable and safe because of the existence of preservative factors or hurdles. The varied nature and strength of these preservative factors synergistically act to control the growth or multiplication of spoilage or pathogenic microorganisms because the organisms are unable to jump over all of the existing hurdles. Results found in conformity with Juvonen *et al.* (2011) in mixed fruit jam and high acidity which prevents the growth of food poisoning bacteria and also helps to maintain the colour and flavour of jam reported by Desalegn *et al.* (2016) in guava jam.

Table 1 Influence of storage period on colour-appearance of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam

Treatments	Colour-appearance					Average score
	Storage period (Days)					
	Fresh	30	60	90	120	
T ₁	8.7	8.5	8.2	8.0	7.9	8.2
T ₂	8.5	8.4	8.1	7.9	7.8	8.1
T ₃	7.8	7.5	7.3	7.0	6.7	7.2
T ₄	7.7	7.4	7.1	6.9	6.6	7.1
T ₅	8.1	8.6	8.2	8.1	7.8	8.1
T ₆	8.8	8.7	8.4	8.2	8.1	8.4
T ₇	8.3	8.2	7.9	7.6	7.4	7.8
T ₈	8.0	7.8	7.7	7.4	7.1	7.6

Table 2 Influence of storage period on texture of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam

Treatments	Texture					Average score
	Storage period (Days)					
	Fresh	30	60	90	120	
T ₁	8.7	8.6	8.5	8.3	8.1	8.4
T ₂	8.6	8.4	8.3	8.1	7.9	8.2
T ₃	8.5	8.3	8.2	8.0	7.8	8.1
T ₄	8.3	8.0	7.7	7.6	7.4	7.8
T ₅	8.0	8.1	8.2	8.5	8.2	8.2
T ₆	9.3	9.1	9.0	8.9	8.8	9.0
T ₇	9.0	8.8	8.7	8.6	8.5	8.7
T ₈	8.8	8.7	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.5

Table 3 Influence of storage period on taste of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam

Treatments	Taste					Average score
	Storage period (Days)					
	Fresh	30	60	90	120	
T ₁	8.9	8.8	8.6	8.5	8.3	8.6
T ₂	8.8	8.6	8.5	8.3	8.1	8.4
T ₃	8.3	8.2	8.0	7.8	7.5	7.9
T ₄	8.0	7.7	7.4	7.3	6.9	7.4
T ₅	8.8	8.7	8.6	8.5	8.4	8.6
T ₆	9.2	9.1	8.8	8.6	8.7	8.8
T ₇	8.5	8.3	8.1	7.9	7.8	8.1
T ₈	8.2	8.1	7.9	7.7	7.4	7.8

Table 4 Influence of storage period on flavour of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam

Treatments	Flavour					Average score
	Storage period (Days)					
	Fresh	30	60	90	120	
T ₁	8.6	8.4	8.3	8.1	7.9	8.2
T ₂	8.3	8.2	8.0	7.9	7.8	8.0
T ₃	8.0	7.8	7.5	7.3	7.1	7.5
T ₄	7.8	7.7	7.4	7.2	6.9	7.4
T ₅	7.9	8.0	8.1	8.1	8.2	8.0
T ₆	9.1	9.0	8.9	8.7	8.7	8.8
T ₇	8.8	8.7	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.5
T ₈	8.7	8.6	8.5	8.3	8.2	8.4

Table 5 Influence of storage period on overall acceptance of beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam

Treatments	Overall acceptability					Average score
	Storage period (Days)					
	Fresh	30	60	90	120	
T ₁	8.8	8.6	8.3	8.2	7.9	8.3
T ₂	8.1	8.2	8.0	7.9	7.8	8.0
T ₃	8.0	7.8	7.5	7.3	7.1	7.5
T ₄	7.8	7.7	7.4	7.2	6.9	7.4
T ₅	8.6	8.5	8.4	8.3	8.2	8.4
T ₆	9.2	9.0	8.8	8.7	8.5	8.8
T ₇	8.9	8.7	8.6	8.4	8.2	8.5
T ₈	8.6	8.4	8.3	8.2	7.9	8.2

Table 6 Microbial growth after 120 days of storage period

Parameters	Microbial count (in cfu/gm.)										
	Treatment (Mean) value										
	T ₁	T ₂	T ₃	T ₄	T ₅	T ₆	T ₇	T ₈	Mean	SE (±)	CD@1%
Yeast and mould ($\times 10^3$ cfu/gm.)	10.68	14	13.30	14.33	10.66	9.3	9.6	10	11.49	0.45	1.8
Coliform ($\times 10^3$ cfu/gm.)	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	NIL	-	-

Conclusion

The investigation results indicates that, sensory score decreased with course of storage period, also different sweetening agents affects the sensory attributes of jam. More specifically treatments having jaggery as sweetening agent found good as compared to treatments having sugar as sweetening agent.

As the minimum changes in sensory qualities for colour-appearance, texture, taste, flavour and overall acceptability were recorded in beetroot-pumpkin mixed jam prepared with 70:30 beetroot-pumpkin pulp ratio and jaggery as sweetening agent and also secured the highest score for sensory qualities for, colour-appearance, texture,

taste, flavour and overall acceptability and ranked 'like extremely' and showed minimum microbial growth after 120 days of storage.

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